

Influence of Parental Engagement Towards Pupils' Social Cognitive Development

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Abstract: This study examined the influence of parental engagement on pupils' social cognitive development. Grounded in the premise that early childhood experiences significantly shape cognitive and social outcomes, the research focused on how parental attitudes and beliefs, school-related involvement, and child-centered practices contribute to the development of social cognition among elementary pupils. A quantitative descriptive-correlational design was employed to determine the relationship between variables. The respondents were 160 parents of elementary pupils from various barangays in Gabaldon, Nueva Ecija, selected through purposive and snowball sampling. Data were collected using a validated and reliable structured questionnaire, with Cronbach's alpha values ranging from .78 to .87, indicating acceptable to good internal consistency. Descriptive statistics, including frequency, percentage, and weighted mean, were used to assess the level of parental engagement and pupils' social cognitive development, while Kendall's tau-b was utilized to determine the relationships among variables. The findings revealed that parents demonstrated a consistently high level of engagement across all domains. Pupils also exhibited a high level of social cognitive development, particularly in cooperative behavior, respect for authority, and self-confidence. Correlation analysis showed that parental attitudes and beliefs ($\tau = .287, p < .001$) and school factors ($\tau = .250, p < .001$) had moderate positive relationships with social cognitive development, while child factors ($\tau = .188, p < .001$) showed a weaker but significant relationship. The study concludes that parental engagement, particularly in attitudes and school involvement, plays a significant role in enhancing pupils' social cognitive development.

Keywords: Parental Engagement, Social Cognitive Development, School Factors, Child Factors, Elementary Pupils.

Introduction

Early childhood is a critical period in human development, during which foundational cognitive, social, and emotional capacities are established. According to UNICEF (2022), the quality of children's early experiences plays a decisive role in brain development, shaping the foundations for lifelong learning, health, and behavior. Likewise, the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (2023) highlights that stable, responsive relationships with parents and supportive environments significantly promote positive developmental outcomes. These early interactions are essential not only for physical and emotional growth but also for the development of social cognition, which enables children to understand, interpret, and respond appropriately within social contexts.

However, despite the importance of nurturing environments, children continue to face various developmental challenges influenced by both internal and external factors. As emphasized by Blatt (2023), children encounter a combination of positive and adverse experiences that may affect their developmental trajectories, including those arising from environments beyond their immediate families. In this regard, parental engagement becomes a crucial determinant in buffering negative influences and fostering children's adaptive social and cognitive skills.

Parental engagement extends beyond monitoring academic performance and includes meaningful involvement such as communication, emotional support, and active participation in children's learning and social experiences. John Hattie and Clinton (2013) emphasize that such engagement fosters positive relationships that inspire, guide, and motivate children. Moreover, social cognition is fundamental to children's ability to build relationships, regulate emotions, and function effectively in social environments. As noted by Anderson (2023), deficits in social cognition can lead to challenges in social competence, behavior, and emotional regulation, highlighting the need for strong parental support during early developmental stages.

While previous studies have acknowledged the role of parental involvement in child development, there remains a gap in understanding how specific dimensions of parental engagement influence pupils' social cognitive development, particularly when considering demographic and contextual factors. Addressing this gap, the present study aims to investigate the influence of parental engagement on pupils' social cognitive development.

Specifically, this study seeks to describe the profile of respondents in terms of age, sex, occupation, monthly income, and the highest educational attainment of parents. It further examines how parental engagement influences pupils' social cognitive development in relation to parental attitudes and beliefs, school factors, and child-related factors. In addition, the study aims to assess the level of pupils' social cognitive development and determine whether a significant

relationship exists between parental engagement and pupils' social cognitive development. Through these inquiries, the research intends to provide a comprehensive understanding of how parental involvement shapes children's social cognitive outcomes and to generate evidence-based insights that may inform educational practices, parental strategies, and policy development.

Methodology

Research Design

The research method used in this study is a quantitative approach, specifically the Descriptive Correlational Design. It provides systematic information about the population, situation, or phenomenon being studied. According to Cherry (2020), a correlational study is a research design that examines the relationships between two or more variables. Correlational studies are non-experimental, meaning the experimenter does not manipulate or control any variables. In relation, this study determined the "Influence of parental engagement towards pupils' social cognitive development.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents in this study were parents of elementary pupils from all barangays of Gabaldon, Nueva Ecija. A total of 160 respondents were included, with 10 parents from each of the 16 barangays to ensure balanced representation across the municipality. Regarding sex distribution, the majority of respondents were female (148), while a smaller proportion were male (12).

The study employed a combination of purposive and snowball sampling techniques. Purposive sampling was used to select parents of elementary pupils who could provide relevant and reliable information aligned with the study's objectives. Meanwhile, snowball sampling was utilized to identify additional qualified respondents through referrals, particularly in areas where initial participants were limited. This combined approach ensured adequate representation across key demographic characteristics, including age, sex, educational attainment, and income levels.

Table 1.

Table of Respondents.

Barangay	Female	Male	Total
Bagong Sikat	9	1	10
Bagting	9	1	10
Bantug	9	1	10
Bugnan	10	0	10
Calabasa	9	1	10
Camachile	10	0	10
Cuyapa	10	0	10
Ligaya	9	1	10
Macasandal	10	0	10
Malinao	10	0	10
North Poblacion	7	3	10
Pantoc	10	0	10
Pinamalisan	9	1	10
Sawmill	9	1	10
South Poblacion	9	1	10
Tagumpay	9	1	10
TOTAL:	148	12	160

Research Instrument

The researchers used a structured survey questionnaire to collect information from the selected respondents. The questionnaire was designed in two parts. The first part is intended to determine the respondents' profiles, and the second section contains questions aligned with the set objectives. The questionnaire was a closed-ended one, in which respondents were allowed to choose an answer from the given scale by filling in and ticking the space provided that corresponded to their answer.

Validity of Research Instrument

The questionnaire used in the study was subjected to validation. Several individuals, including the researcher's adviser, the researcher's instructor, and the faculty of the College of Education, NEUST Gabaldon campus, evaluated the research instruments for face validity. Copies of the questionnaire were handed to an English critic and a research adviser, who carefully reviewed the questions to assess the suitability and sufficiency of the instruments.

Reliability of Research Instrument

The researchers used Cronbach's Alpha to measure the internal consistency of the questionnaire items and assess how closely related they are within the scale. Cronbach's alpha measures reliability by comparing the covariance among items to the overall variance, ensuring a high degree of correlation among items for credibility.

Cronbach's Alpha ranges between 0 and 1, with 0 being the lowest possible value and 1 being the highest. A value of 0 indicates no internal consistency or reliability in the questionnaire, while a value of 1 indicates perfect internal consistency. A score close to 1 indicates that the questionnaire items are highly correlated with one another and provide a consistent measure of the underlying construct. In contrast, a score close to 0 indicates that the items are not well-correlated and do not provide a consistent measure of the construct.

The reliability test of parental attitudes and beliefs yielded a value of 0.84, indicating a "Good" result. Followed by the school factors, which obtained a value of 0.83, indicating that the result is also "Good". Child factors obtained a value of 0.87, also suggesting that the result is "Good". Lastly, social cognitive development obtained a value of 0.78, signifying that the result is "Acceptable".

Procedure of the Study

The study entitled "Influence of Parental Engagement towards Pupils' Social Cognitive Development" was conducted with the following procedure. After the title was approved, the researcher proceeded to chapter 1, which covered the problem and its surroundings. The researchers emphasized ethical concerns and obtained the necessary permits, including the letter addressed to the parents. Once permission was granted, the researchers developed a questionnaire measuring the influence of parental engagement on pupils' Social Cognitive Development. The researchers then compiled the relevant literature, developed a study protocol, analyzed and interpreted the data, evaluated the results, and drew conclusions.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The collected data were analyzed using quantitative and descriptive statistical approaches. Descriptive statistics, including frequency counts, percentages, and weighted means, were used to present and summarize data collected from respondents via structured questionnaires. Specifically, frequency and percentage distribution were employed to describe the profile of the respondents. To assess the level of parental engagement, frequency distributions, percentages, and weighted means were used. Furthermore, the effectiveness of parental engagement in influencing pupils' social cognitive development was determined by computing and interpreting weighted mean scores. A four-point Likert scale was used in the questionnaire, with each point corresponding to a specific level of response to ensure consistent data measurement and interpretation. In terms of level of frequency, the scale was interpreted as follows: a mean score of 3.26–4.00 indicates "Always," 2.51–3.25 indicates "Often," 1.76–2.50 indicates "Rarely," and 1.00–1.75 indicates "Never."

Ethics in Research

According to Fleming and Zegwaard (2018), it is important to further consider the fundamentals of ethical research involving human participants. Thus, ethical research is considered as one that does not cause harm, stress, and discomfort; secures informed consent from participants, subjects, or respondents; and respects the rights of individuals being studied. Ethical considerations are vital for researchers to give serious thought to at every stage of this study.

Therefore, the use of offensive, discriminatory, or other unacceptable language was avoided in the formulation of the questionnaire. The researchers considered the principle of informed consent to provide sufficient information and assurance about taking part to allow respondents to understand the implications and to obtain a fully informed, considered, and freely given decision about whether or not to do so, without the exercise of any pressure or coercion.

In this study, the researchers informed the respondents that their participation was voluntary and that they were free to omit answers to any particular questions. Moreover, participants have the right to withdraw from the study at any

time. This is in line with Dudovskiy, who argued that the voluntary participation of respondents in the research is important. The researcher also protected the identity of the participants, and the data disclosed was kept with utmost confidentiality in respect and consideration to the privacy of the respondents. Lastly, the researchers avoided plagiarism and fraud by acknowledging the works of other authors used in any part of this study.

Results

Profile of the Respondents

The demographic profile of the respondents was analyzed with respect to age, sex, occupation, monthly income, and educational attainment (N = 160). The majority of the respondents were aged 30–39 years (n = 75, 46.9%). This was followed by those aged 20–29 years (n = 32, 20.0%) and 40–49 years (n = 31, 19.4%). The smallest proportion belonged to the 50 and above category (n = 22, 13.8%). Regarding sex, most respondents were female (n = 148, 92.5%), while only a small proportion were male (n = 12, 7.5%).

Regarding occupation, the largest group of respondents was unemployed (n = 101, 63.1%). This was followed by those engaged in farming (n = 26, 16.3%) and business (n = 20, 12.5%). A smaller number were laborers (n = 9, 5.6%), while the least represented were government employees (n = 4, 2.5%). In terms of family income classification, the majority of respondents were categorized as poor (less than ₱9,100) (n = 111, 69.4%). This was followed by those in the low-income group (₱9,100–₱18,200) (n = 42, 26.3%). Only a small percentage belonged to the middle class (₱36,400–₱63,700) (n = 7, 4.4%).

Regarding educational attainment, most respondents had completed secondary education (n = 82, 51.25%). This was followed by those with elementary education (n = 32, 20.0%) and undergraduate level education (n = 26, 16.25%). A smaller proportion had upper secondary education (n = 8, 5.0%) and vocational training (n = 6, 3.75%).

Table 2.

Profile of the Respondents.

Age	Frequency	Percentage
20 - 29	32	20
30 - 39	75	46.9
40 - 49	31	19.4
50 and above	22	13.8
Total	160	100
Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	12	7.5
Female	148	92.5
Total	160	100
Occupation	Frequency	Percentage
Laborer	9	5.6
Government Employee	4	2.5
Farming	26	16.3
Business	20	12.5
Unemployed	101	63.1
Total	160	100
Family Class (Monthly Income)	Frequency	Percentage
Middle Class (36,400 - 63,700)	7	4.4
Low income (9,100 - 18,200)	42	26.3
Poor (less than 9,100)	111	69.4
Total	160	100
Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percentage
Elementary	32	20
Secondary	82	51.25
Upper Secondary	8	5
Vocational	6	3.75
Undergraduate	26	16.25
Total	160	100

Influence of parental engagement on pupils' social cognitive development

The influence of parental engagement on pupils' social cognitive development was examined across the following factors: parental attitudes and beliefs, school factors, and child factors.

Parental attitudes and beliefs

Table 3 presents the level of parental attitudes and beliefs in relation to pupils' social cognitive development. All indicators were interpreted as "Always," indicating a consistently high level of parental engagement in this domain. The highest-rated item was actively listening to the child's concerns without judgment ($M = 3.85$, Rank 1), followed by parental involvement in school activities ($M = 3.84$, Rank 2). Both providing guidance on building positive peer relationships and modeling positive social behavior ranked third ($M = 3.81$).

Other highly rated indicators included supporting the child's empathy development ($M = 3.79$, Rank 5) and encouraging participation in social interactions outside the family ($M = 3.79$, Rank 6). Meanwhile, reinforcing values such as kindness and respect ($M = 3.76$, Rank 7) and reinforcing cultural values ($M = 3.72$, Rank 8) also received high ratings. The lowest-rated items, though still interpreted as "Always," were engaging in conversations about emotions ($M = 3.60$, Rank 9) and dedicating time to discuss social concerns within the family ($M = 3.58$, Rank 10). Overall, the results indicate that parents consistently demonstrate positive attitudes and beliefs that support their children's social cognitive development.

Table 3.

Parental Attitudes and Beliefs.

Attitudes and beliefs	Weighted Mean	Rank	Verbal Description
1. I engage in conversations with my child about their emotions and feelings.	3.60	9	Always
2. I dedicate time for my family to discuss any concerns or issues related to my child's social interactions.	3.58	10	Always
3. I reinforce values such as kindness, respect, and cooperation with my child.	3.76	7	Always
4. I provide guidance to my child on building positive relationships with peers.	3.81	3	Always
5. I support my child in developing empathy and understanding towards others.	3.79	5	Always
6. I reinforce cultural values, beliefs, and aspects with my child.	3.72	8	Always
7. I believe that involving my child in social events and interactions outside the family setting is beneficial for their development.	3.79	6	Always
8. I believe that modeling positive social behavior and interpersonal skills positively influences my child's social cognitive development.	3.81	3	Always
9. I believe that actively listening to my child's concerns without judgement is crucial for their social cognitive development.	3.85	1	Always
10. I believe that my involvement in my child's school activities positively influences their social cognitive growth.	3.84	2	Always

School Factors

Table 4 presents parental engagement in terms of school-related factors influencing pupils' social cognitive development. All items were interpreted as "Always," indicating a consistently high level of parental involvement in school-related activities. The highest-rated item was encouraging the child to participate in extracurricular activities ($M = 3.78$, Rank 1), followed by being informed about school activities and upcoming events ($M = 3.73$, Rank 2) and assisting the child with homework and academic requirements ($M = 3.68$, Rank 3).

Moderately high ratings were observed in communication with teachers regarding academic and social progress ($M = 3.61$, Rank 4) and collaboration with other parents ($M = 3.60$, Rank 5). Engagement in discussions with school staff about a positive and inclusive environment ($M = 3.52$, Rank 6) and providing feedback to the school ($M = 3.51$, Rank 7) were also consistently practiced.

Lower-ranked but still highly practiced activities included attendance in parent-teacher conferences ($M = 3.48$, Rank 8) and participation in school events ($M = 3.38$, Rank 9). The lowest-rated item was volunteering time in school activities or projects ($M = 3.26$, Rank 10). Overall, the findings indicate that parents are actively engaged in school-related factors that support their children's social cognitive development.

Table 4.

School Factors.

School factors	Weighted Mean	Rank	Verbal Description
1. I attend parent-teacher conferences or meetings at my child's school.	3.48	8	Always
2. I participate in school events, such as fundraisers, sports events, or cultural celebrations.	3.38	9	Always
3. I communicate with my child's teachers to discuss their academic and social progress.	3.61	4	Always
4. I volunteer my time at the school, assisting with activities or projects.	3.26	10	Always
5. I am informed about my child's school activities and upcoming events.	3.73	2	Always
6. I collaborate with other parents to create a supportive community within the school.	3.60	5	Always
7. I assist my child with homework and/or other academic requirements.	3.68	3	Always
8. I encourage my child to participate in extracurricular activities offered by the school.	3.78	1	Always
9. I provide feedback or suggestions to the school regarding their programs and policies.	3.51	7	Always
10. I actively engage in discussions with school staff about fostering a positive and inclusive school environment.	3.52	6	Always

Child Factors

Table 5 presents parental engagement in terms of child-related factors influencing pupils' social cognitive development. All items were interpreted as "Always," indicating consistently high parental involvement in direct interactions with their children.

The highest-rated item was reinforcing positive behavior and values (e.g., kindness, respect, and empathy) ($M = 3.87$, Rank 1). This was followed by fostering family connection through joint activities ($M = 3.84$, Rank 2) and discussing responsibility and accountability ($M = 3.84$, Rank 3). Several indicators shared similar high ratings, including providing opportunities for diverse social interactions ($M = 3.81$, Rank 4), discussing school-related challenges ($M = 3.81$, Rank 4), and actively listening to the child's school experiences ($M = 3.81$, Rank 6).

Other practices, such as encouraging emotional expression ($M = 3.78$, Rank 7) and assisting in setting social and academic goals ($M = 3.75$, Rank 8), were also consistently observed. The lowest-rated items, though still interpreted as "Always," involved the child in decision-making ($M = 3.66$, Rank 9) and participating in the child's hobbies outside school ($M = 3.65$, Rank 10). Overall, the results indicate that parents are highly engaged in practices that directly support their children's social cognitive development.

Table 5.*Child Factors*

Child factors	Weighted Mean	Rank	Verbal Description
1. I actively listen to my child's thoughts and opinions about their school experiences.	3.81	6	Always
2. I involve my child in decision-making processes related to their education and activities.	3.66	9	Always
3. I encourage my child to express their feelings and emotions openly at home.	3.78	7	Always
4. I participate in my child's hobbies or interests outside of school.	3.65	10	Always
5. I assist my child in setting and achieving social and academic goals.	3.75	8	Always
6. I discuss with my child the importance of responsibility and accountability in their actions.	3.84	3	Always
7. I provide opportunities for my child to interact with diverse groups of people to enhance their social skills.	3.81	4	Always
8. I reinforce positive behavior and values, such as kindness, respect, and empathy, with my child.	3.87	1	Always
9. I foster a sense of family connection and support through engaging in joint activities with my child.	3.84	2	Always
10. I discuss any challenges or concerns my child may be facing in their school life.	3.81	4	Always

Social Cognitive Development of the Pupils

Table 6 presents the level of pupils' social cognitive development as perceived by parents. All indicators were interpreted as "Always," indicating a consistently high level of social cognitive development among the pupils. The highest-rated indicator was engaging in cooperative play with others (M = 3.93, Rank 1), followed by respecting authority figures (M = 3.92, Rank 2) and demonstrating self-confidence (M = 3.91, Rank 3).

Other highly rated indicators included curiosity and desire to learn (M = 3.85, Rank 4) and taking responsibility for actions (M = 3.84, Rank 5). Moderately high ratings were observed in understanding different perspectives (M = 3.78, Rank 6), positive peer interaction (M = 3.78, Rank 7), and demonstrating empathy (M = 3.75, Rank 8). Additional indicators such as adaptability (M = 3.74, Rank 9) and openness to new experiences (M = 3.73, Rank 10) were also consistently evident.

Lower-ranked indicators, though still interpreted as "Always," included communication skills (M = 3.70, Rank 11), independence in tasks (M = 3.67, Rank 12), and emotional expression (M = 3.62, Rank 13). The lowest-rated indicators were conflict management (M = 3.59, Rank 14) and resilience in facing challenges (M = 3.51, Rank 15). Overall, the findings indicate that pupils demonstrate strong social cognitive development across various domains.

Table 6.*Social Cognitive Development.*

Social Cognitive Development	Weighted Mean	Rank	Verbal Description
1. My child demonstrates empathy towards others.	3.75	8	Always
2. My child is able to express their emotions effectively.	3.62	13	Always
3. My child interacts positively with peers.	3.78	7	Always
4. My child is open to trying new experiences.	3.73	10	Always
5. My child shows independence in completing tasks.	3.67	12	Always
6. My child is able to adapt to new situations.	3.74	9	Always
7. My child respects authority figures (teachers, parents, etc.)	3.92	2	Always
8. My child demonstrates good communication skills.	3.70	11	Always

Table 6 Continued.

9. My child is able to handle conflicts appropriately.	3.59	14	Always
10. My child shows resilience in the face of challenges.	3.51	15	Always
11. My child exhibits curiosity and a desire to learn.	3.85	4	Always
12. My child shows interest in understanding different perspectives.	3.78	6	Always
13. My child demonstrates self-confidence in their abilities.	3.91	3	Always
14. My child engages in cooperative play with others.	3.93	1	Always
15. My child takes responsibility for their actions.	3.84	5	Always

Relationship Between the Level of Parental Engagement and Pupil's Social Cognitive Development

Table 7 presents the relationship between parental engagement variables and pupils' social cognitive development using Kendall's tau-b correlation. The results reveal that parental attitudes and beliefs have a statistically significant relationship with pupils' social cognitive development ($\tau = .287, p < .001$). Similarly, school factors also show a significant relationship ($\tau = .250, p < .001$). Meanwhile, child factors demonstrate a significant but comparatively weaker relationship ($\tau = .188, p < .001$). Overall, all dimensions of parental engagement were found to have significant positive relationships with pupils' social cognitive development.

Table 7.

Correlation of parental engagement and pupil's social cognitive development.

Variables	Kendall's tau-b (τ)	p-value	Interpretation
Parental Attitudes and Beliefs	.287**	< .001	Significant
School Factors	.250**	< .001	Significant
Child Factors	.188**	< .001	Significant

Discussion

The results show that respondents were predominantly female, aged 30–39 years, unemployed, from low-income households, and with secondary-level education. These characteristics provide an important context for understanding parental engagement in relation to pupils' social cognitive development. Most respondents were within the 30–39 age group, which is associated with active parenting and greater involvement in children's development (Thompson & Brown, 2021). Moreover, the dominance of female respondents reflects traditional caregiving roles, where mothers are more engaged in nurturing and developmental support (Eagly & Wood, 2013).

In addition, the high proportion of unemployed respondents suggests increased availability for childcare, which may enhance parent-child interaction (Andersen, 2013). Despite the majority belonging to low-income households, research indicates that economically disadvantaged parents often foster strong relationships and communication that support children's development (Scholar & Partner, 2019). Furthermore, the prevalence of secondary-level education implies that respondents possess sufficient foundational knowledge to support their children's cognitive and social growth (Havighurst & Thorpe, 2015). Taken together, these findings suggest that parental engagement remains significant despite socioeconomic constraints.

Building on this context, the findings further reveal that parents exhibit strong and consistent positive attitudes and beliefs, particularly in active listening, school involvement, and modeling appropriate social behavior. The high rating for nonjudgmental listening highlights the importance of open communication and emotional support in developing children's social understanding. This aligns with Nnamani et al. (2016), who emphasized that parental engagement through listening, encouragement, and positive interaction fosters children's emotional adjustment and social competence. Similarly, Morelli et al. (2015) noted that when children feel heard and understood, they are more likely to develop strong communication skills and trusting relationships. Although all indicators were rated highly, slightly lower engagement in family discussions about social concerns suggests an area for improvement, though overall parental attitudes remain a strong contributor to social cognitive development.

Consistent with these findings, parents also demonstrated strong involvement in school-related activities, particularly in encouraging participation in extracurricular activities, staying informed, and supporting academic tasks. The emphasis on extracurricular involvement underscores its importance in developing children's social and personal skills. This supports Anglia (2022), which highlighted that extracurricular activities promote lifelong skills, social

competence, and personal growth. Through these activities, children develop teamwork, leadership, and emotional skills essential for social cognitive development. However, slightly lower engagement in volunteering and participation in school events may be influenced by time constraints, economic limitations, or accessibility. Nevertheless, school-related parental engagement remains a significant factor in supporting pupils' development.

In parallel, the findings also indicate that parents are highly engaged in child-centered practices, particularly in reinforcing positive values, strengthening family relationships, and promoting responsibility. The emphasis on value reinforcement highlights the role of parents as primary social models shaping children's behavior and social understanding. This is supported by Eisenberg et al. (2014), who emphasized that children acquire prosocial behaviors such as empathy and respect through parental modeling. Likewise, Jandial (2023) noted that parenting behaviors and interactions significantly influence children's personality development and social competence. Although involvement in decision-making and participation in hobbies were relatively lower, these remain areas where parental engagement can be further strengthened.

As a result of these parental practices, pupils were found to exhibit high levels of social cognitive development, particularly in cooperative play, respect for authority, and self-confidence. The prominence of cooperative play highlights its role in fostering social interaction, empathy, and collaboration skills. This finding is consistent with Spinrad et al. (2014), who reported that cooperative play enhances empathy and prosocial behavior. Similarly, Jenkins and Astington (2021) emphasized that collaborative play promotes communication, conflict resolution, and social problem-solving skills, while Carpenter and Tomasello (2017) highlighted its role in developing perspective-taking abilities. Although resilience and conflict management were comparatively lower, the overall results indicate strong social cognitive development among pupils.

Finally, the correlation results confirm that all aspects of parental engagement significantly influence pupils' social cognitive development, with parental attitudes and beliefs and school-related involvement showing stronger associations. This suggests that supportive, nurturing, and value-oriented parenting practices, along with active school participation, are critical in shaping children's social understanding and behavior. This supports Garcia and Hernandez (2020), who emphasized the importance of positive parental attitudes, while Lee and Chang (2017) noted that negative or inconsistent parenting may hinder development. Furthermore, positive school environments characterized by supportive teachers and inclusive interactions contribute to improved social cognitive outcomes (Brown & Smith, 2016; Wang et al., 2019). Although child factors showed a weaker relationship, individual characteristics such as temperament and emotional regulation still contribute to development (Chen & Liu, 2021; Davis & Nguyen, 2014; Thompson & Martinez, 2016). Overall, the findings underscore the interconnected roles of home and school environments, highlighting that strong parental engagement remains a key factor in fostering pupils' social cognitive development.

Conclusion

The findings revealed that the respondents were predominantly female, within the 30–39 age group, unemployed, from low-income households, and with secondary-level education. Despite socioeconomic constraints, parents demonstrated a consistently high level of engagement across all dimensions, including parental attitudes and beliefs, school-related involvement, and child-centered practices.

Results showed that parents strongly exhibited positive attitudes and beliefs, particularly in active listening, value formation, and involvement in school activities. Similarly, high levels of engagement were observed in school factors, especially in encouraging participation in extracurricular activities and supporting academic tasks. In terms of child factors, parents were highly involved in reinforcing positive behavior, fostering family relationships, and guiding their children in taking on responsibility.

Furthermore, pupils demonstrated a high level of social cognitive development, particularly in cooperative play, respect for authority, self-confidence, and curiosity. However, relatively lower levels were observed in resilience and conflict management, indicating areas for further enhancement.

Correlation analysis revealed that all dimensions of parental engagement were statistically significantly related to pupils' social cognitive development. Parental attitudes and beliefs and school factors showed moderate positive relationships, while child factors exhibited a weaker but still significant relationship. These findings highlight that environmental influences, particularly parenting practices and school involvement, play a more substantial role in shaping social cognitive outcomes than individual child characteristics alone.

Overall, the study concludes that parental engagement is a significant determinant of pupils' social cognitive development, emphasizing the importance of fostering strong home–school partnerships and positive parenting practices to support children's holistic development.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, it is recommended that parents continue to strengthen their engagement in their children's development by maintaining positive attitudes, practicing active listening, and consistently reinforcing values such as respect, empathy, and responsibility. Parents are also encouraged to increase their involvement in school-related activities, such as attending conferences, participating in school programs, and collaborating with teachers and other parents, as these were found to significantly support pupils' social cognitive development. Schools, on the other hand, should design and implement programs that actively promote parent participation, including workshops, parenting seminars, and community-building activities that enhance home-school partnerships. In addition, educators should integrate activities that develop pupils' resilience, conflict management, and emotional expression, as these areas were identified as relatively lower compared to other aspects of social cognitive development. Policymakers and school administrators may also consider providing support mechanisms for low-income families, such as accessible school engagement initiatives and flexible participation opportunities, to ensure inclusive parental involvement. Lastly, future researchers are encouraged to explore other variables that may influence social cognitive development, such as teacher factors, peer interactions, and environmental conditions, as well as to employ longitudinal or mixed-method approaches to gain a deeper understanding of the long-term effects of parental engagement.

Author Contributions

The study was completed through equal collaboration between the two authors. One primarily handled supervision, validation, and the review process, while the other led the data collection, analysis, and writing of the manuscript.

Conflict of Interest Statement

The author declares no competing interests.

AI Use Declaration

Language editing was supported using an AI tool, specifically ChatGPT (OpenAI, version 5). The authors carefully reviewed all outputs and assume full responsibility for the final content.

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